

Framework of the Open Access modules

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Annotation

The purpose of the annotation is to introduce and promote the module. The annotation is structured around the module's main objective and outcomes.

Prerequisite for the module

- Indicate the necessary preparation, i.e. what knowledge you need to have before you start studying.
- Provide a list of sources to help students find the information and knowledge they need.

Pre-reading list (optional)

List of sources recommended to be read before starting the module

Objective of the module

- The objective of the module is to provide, in a single sentence and in general terms, a substantive, qualitative, forward-looking outcome for the whole module.
- Describe the goals and intentions of the instructor.
- Focus on content and skills important within the classroom or programme.
- Should be specific and detailed.
- The objective is expressed in terms of process-oriented actions: to introduce ...; to provide knowledge about ...; to develop skills etc.

Learning outcomes

- Student learning outcomes are the evidence that the objectives were achieved.
- Learning outcomes are designed from the students' perspective, describing what students should be able to do after completing a module.
- The design of the module starts with the learning outcomes, aligning each learning outcome with the learning methods and methods of assessing student achievement.
- Outcomes are exactly what assessments are intended to show – specifically what the student will be able to do upon completing the course. Outcomes are clear and measurable criteria for guiding the teaching, learning, and assessment process in the course.
- An assessable outcome can be displayed or observed and evaluated against criteria.

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- The module outcomes are constructed using Bloom's taxonomy according to the complexity of the competences achieved by the student.
- The formulation of the learning outcome of a module starts with a verb describing the ability, which describes the action performed by the student: able to define, classify, measure, use, group, organise, prepare, coordinate, construct, design, etc.

Learning objectives and outcomes terms are sometimes used as synonymous. Objectives, comprising aims or goals, and Outcomes, comprising tangible results, may overlap, but are not the same.

When designing training, we should think primarily of objectives, then list what outcomes you want our audience to reach for. In most cases, an objective encloses one or more outcomes.

All practical exercises should be designed around specific outcomes.

Methods for study or self-study

- The methods of study or self-study must be related to the module learning outcomes.
- The study process must include a variety of study methods: reading material on your student's own, interactive lectures, practical sessions, information retrieval, exercises, case studies, problem analysis and solving sessions, individual and group work, report presentation, tutorials, etc.
- The study method is based on a series of activities, the assessment of the results of which must be consistent with the nature of the activities involved. For example, if the method of study is a case study, the recommended assessment methods may be a report, an oral illustrated presentation, reflection on the activity.

Learning / training materials (2-3 pages with links to references)

- Developing a learning / training course requires gathering and preparing content. A lot of content is now available on the internet and it is not so much a question of finding or creating content, but of finding the right content, or adapting the discovered content to the needs and capabilities of the target audience.
- One of the biggest challenges in developing training courses is reducing content to a training format. If you only need to produce a two-hour training course, you need to provide the most relevant information on a given topic in that time.
- However, as a trainer you usually have much more knowledge to impart. Try to reduce the content to the most important key points. What is essential to know and what are just details or minor topics?
- Prioritise topics, be transparent about missed topics and inform the participants.
- Sufficient time should be left for open questions, discussion and sharing of experiences among participants.

Video (optional)

A short video introducing the structure of the module, the objective, the content and the expected outcomes of the module.

Assignments

- Practical assignments are provided to ensure that learners have acquired the necessary skills and can apply them in practice.
- 2-3 practical exercises are presented.
- Guidance on how to complete the assignments or answers are provided.

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Self-check questions

- As Provide a list of questions for learners to answer in order to test their knowledge.
- Self-test answers are provided as links to learning materials or other online resources.

Further readings

The further readings consist of 5-7 sources that provide sufficient coverage of all or some of the module topics. These sources must be available in open-access or electronic form. It is recommended that the sources should be at least 5-10 years old. It is recommended that the sources are no older than 5-10 years.

Adapted from:

<http://provost.rpi.edu/learning-assessment/learning-outcomes/objectives-vsoutcomes>

<https://www.fosteropenscience.eu/content/open-science-training-handbook>

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